

Reaction of Hydrazoic Acid with Oxazolones

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Recently the reaction explored by Jennings¹ for the conversion of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde to *m*-nitrophenylacetic acid has been successfully used for preparing 2-benzofurylacetic acids² from 2-formylbenzofurans. The procedure involves conversion of the azlactone of a 2-formylbenzofuran to the hydrazide which furnishes the azide by reacting with nitrous acid. The azide undergoes the Curtius rearrangement in hot benzene to provide the oxadiazine, hydrolysis of which furnishes a 2-benzofurylacetic acid in good yield. The method is preferable to the old one in spite of the greater number of steps involved.

With a view to minimising the number of steps in this sequence, the reaction of hydrazoic acid on a few azlactones (Table I) has been studied. The reaction proceeds to furnish the azide directly, which on heating in benzene provides the oxadiazine.

As the yields of the oxadiazine are not significantly affected, the hydrazide stage in the above sequence can be avoided by directly changing the azlactone to the azide.

Procedure.—To a suspension of the finely powdered azlactone (0.15*M*) in distilled acetic acid (75 ml) was added sodium azide (0.15 *M*). The mixture was vigorously stirred till the colour of the azlactone was discharged. The solid product, generally, in yellow colour, was collected, washed well with water, and dried in air. As the crude azide was difficult to purify, its formation was judged by its conversion to the oxadiazine.

(a). The azide was extracted from the Soxhlet thimble with benzene. When concentrated and cooled, the benzene extracts deposited the oxadiazine which was recrystallised from benzene.

(b). When the azide was heated, it first melted with effervescence and then solidified. It was recrystallised from benzene affording oxadiazine, identical to the one obtained by method (a).

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1612.

2. Deorha and Gupta, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 371.

A few oxadiazines prepared by this procedure are described in Table I.

TABLE I
Oxadiazines.

*Azlactones used (a).	Oxadiazines formed (b).	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1 ³	R ₁ =CH:Me ₂ ; R ₃ =H; R ₂ =R ₄ =Me.	226°	Deep-yellow	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂	7.72	7.48
2 ³	R ₁ =CH:Me ₂ ; R ₄ =OMe; R ₂ =R ₃ =H.	208°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂	7.81	7.44
3 ³	R ₁ =Et; R ₃ =Cl; R ₂ =R ₄ =Me.	246°	Orange	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	7.31	7.09
4 ³	R ₁ =CH:Me ₂ ; R ₄ =Me; R ₂ =R ₃ =H.	200°	Deep yellow	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂	7.42	7.77
5 ³	R ₁ =Et; R ₃ =H; R ₂ =R ₄ =Me.	174°	Red	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂	7.98	7.77
6 ²	R ₁ =R ₄ =Me; R ₃ =Cl; R ₂ =H.	262°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	7.86	7.64
7 ⁴	R ₁ =Et; R ₂ =H; R ₃ =Cl; R ₄ =Me.	233°	Yellow	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	7.12	7.36
8 ⁵	R ₁ =Me; R ₃ =Cl; R ₂ =R ₄ =H.	251-52°	Orange-yellow	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.19	7.94
9 ⁶	R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H.	222-23°	Orange	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂	8.51	8.80

*Groups correspond to those in the column of oxadiazines. Suffixes refer to reference number.

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, for providing facilities and to the authorities of the University of Rajasthan for awarding a scholarship to one of them (P.G.).

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Received July 7, 1964.

3. Dean *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 327.
4. Doerha and Gupta, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1964, 83, 1056.
5. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 459.
6. *Idem*, *Chem. Ber.*, 1964, 97, 3577.